

bank around a monitoring trap containing 100 µg attractant.

Males caught were counted daily

from 10 days before application to 15 days after. The ability of male moths to locate the trap source was suppressed at

30 mg for 7-10 days (see table). The pheromone had lost much of its disruptive effect 10 days after application. ■

Soil and crop management

Nitrogen management in flooded rice

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A field experiment on flooded rice in the 1981 monsoon season evaluated urea briquet placement (5 cm below soil surface), margosa seedcake-coated urea, shellac-coated urea, sulfur-coated urea, farmyard manure (FYM) + urea, and urea split application. Experimental field soil was silty clay loam (Mollisol). Each nitrogen source was applied at 60 kg N/ha.

There was no yield advantage in 3 split applications of urea over 2 splits at 60 kg N/ha (see table). Margosa seedcake-coated urea and shellac-coated urea also did not offer any significant improvement in yield over urea applied in three split doses. Urea + FYM was equal to urea alone (3 splits).

Sulfur-coated urea produced significantly higher yields than did ordinary urea applied in three split doses. Urea briquet placement 1 week after trans-

Yield of rough rice at 60 kg N/ha.^a

Nitrogen source	Method and time of application	Grain yield (t/ha)	N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
None	—	3.32	—
Urea	Broadcast, 3 splits	3.98	11
Urea	Broadcast, 2 splits (transplanting and tiller initiation)	4.21	15
Urea	Broadcast, 2 splits (tiller initiation and panicle initiation)	4.24	15
Urea briquet	Placement at 5 cm, 1 wk after transplanting	4.85	25
Urea briquet	Placement at 5 cm, 3 wk after transplanting	5.37	34
Margosa seedcake-coated urea	Broadcast at transplanting	3.98	11
Margosa seedcake-coated urea	Broadcast 2 splits (transplanting and tiller initiation)	3.81	8
Shellac-coated urea	Broadcast at transplanting	4.24	15
Sulfur-coated urea	Broadcast at transplanting	4.43	18
FYM + urea (30 + 30)	Broadcast and mixed in soil before transplanting	3.64	5
FYM + urea (30 + 30)	FYM mixed with soil before transplanting and urea broadcast 3 wk after transplanting	3.99	11
S.Em ±		0.15	—
C.D. 5%		0.45	—

^aFYM = farmyard manure.

planting was also significantly superior to ordinary urea (2 or 3 splits), but gave lower yields than placement 3 weeks after transplanting — probably because of the relatively long growth period (144 days) of the rice variety (Jaya) grown.

The highest yield was with urea briquet placement 3 weeks after transplanting.

Nitrogen use efficiency with urea briquet was more than 2 times as high as 2 or 3 split applications of ordinary urea. ■

Algae in rice fields of Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, India

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Samples of algae were collected during October and November 1981 (monsoon season). Rainfall during the period was 370.9 mm, maximum temperature range was 39.0°-25.5° C, and minimum temperature range was 24.5°-16.5° C. Standing water of 1-2 cm was maintained in the fields by lift irrigation from an open well.

Abundance of nitrogen-fixing algae (Cyanophyta species). Tamil Nadu, India.

Species	Relative abundance ^a
<i>Gloeocapsa decorticans</i>	x
<i>Anabaena oryzae</i>	xx
<i>Cylindrospermum muscicola</i>	x
<i>Nostoc sphaericum</i>	x
<i>Aulosira prolifica</i>	x
<i>Calothrix</i> sp.	

^ax = rare, xx = moderate.

Species of algae identified consisted of 11 Cyanophyta, 6 Chlorophyta, 2 Euglenophyta, and 5 Bacillariophyta. Of the 11 Cyanophyta species, 6 are known to be nitrogen-fixing algae (see table). ■

Effect of seedling age on susceptibility to aluminum toxicity

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Although aluminum toxicity is rarely a problem in wetland rice, it may impair growth even in flooded soils when soil pH remains low because of strong acidity and low microbial activity. Relatively young seedlings may fail to establish on some acid sulfate soils.

Solution culture technique was used to examine the effect of seedling age on

susceptibility to aluminum toxicity. Two varieties (IR26 and IR36), 3 plant ages (10-, 20-, and 30-day-old seedlings), and 3 aluminum concentrations (0, 30, and 60 ppm) were used. At a specified plant age, seedlings were transferred to a plastic tray containing culture solution and different levels of aluminum. They were grown for 14 days in a glasshouse room maintained at 29°/21° C (day/night) with natural light and 70% relative humidity.

IR26 and IR36 showed a similar trend. A larger difference was found in shoot weight than in root weight (see table). Stunted growth in 10-day-old seedlings was noticed at 60 ppm Al.

Effect of seedling age and aluminum concentration on average root and shoot weights of 2 rice varieties grown in culture solution at IRR1.^a

Seedling age (days)	Al added (ppm)	Root weight		Shoot weight	
		mg/plant	% of check	mg/plant	% of check
10	0	83	100	266	100
	30	69	83	171	64
	60	62	74	132	49
20	0	298	100	908	100
	30	272	91	878	96
	60	238	79	830	91
30	0	677	100	2143	100
	30	544	80	2032	94
	60	499	73	2159	100

^aFigures are mean values of IR26 and IR36.

These results indicate that, in soils where aluminum toxicity is a potential problem, planting dapog (about 11 days

old) seedlings is not advisable. Twenty-day-old or even older seedlings would minimize risk of stand failure. ■

Comparison of zinc sulfate and Zn-EDTA as foliar spray

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Chelated formulations of zinc (particularly Zn-EDTA) have been recommended as foliar spray. The absorption efficiencies of Zn-EDTA and conventional ZnSO₄ + lime spray were compared in a pot experiment.

A silty clay loam soil containing 1.30 ppm DTPA extractable Zn was used at 2 kg/pot. Two 20-day-old Jaya seedlings in each of 20 pots were sprayed with one of 5 Zn treatments 15 days after transplanting. Treatments, replicated 4 times, were: control (no Zn); 100 ppm Zn as 0.044% ZnSO₄ + 0.022% lime spray; 100 ppm Zn as chelated Zn (manufacturer's recommended rate); 1,130 ppm Zn as 0.5 ZnSO₄ + 0.25% lime (recommended spray), and 1,130 ppm Zn as chelated zinc (Sukshmin-Z).

Both ZnSO₄ and chelated Zn foliar spray increased dry matter and Zn uptake over the control (Fig. 1). Yield with 100 ppm chelated Zn was 37% higher than the control. Dry matter yield and Zn uptake did not differ significantly with 100 ppm and 1,130 ppm Zn as ZnSO₄, nor with 100 ppm and 1,130 ppm chelated Zn.

1. Effect of zinc foliar sprays on rice dry matter yield and zinc uptake.

2. Effect of zinc foliar sprays on rice uptake of copper, iron, and manganese.